

Paper 7

THE PERFORMANCE OF THE VARIOUS CHARGE CONTROLLERS- A REVIEW STUDY

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Abstract:

The charge controller in a solar system plays an important role in filling the battery backup. The charge controller needs to give the controlled output to the battery until the battery is fully charged. When the battery is charged the charge controller usually stops charging the battery. The solar charge controller usually contribute to the efficiency of the performance of the solar system. Usually the solar system has an efficiency of 18% to 20%. There are various factors effecting the efficiency of the solar system. One of the factor being the performance of the solar charge controller. Today in the market we get three types of solar battery chargers namely transistor shunt type which uses a simple transistor acting like a switch to control the charging of the battery, PWM charge controller which uses a Pulse Width Modulation technique to charge a battery having more efficiency than an ordinary transistor based charging and presently MPPT charge controller which transfers the maximum power from the solar panel to the storage as well as output load. This paper contains the review of all those charge controllers. The performance of those charge controllers is discussed. The limitation of these charge controllers are also discussed. The paper leads to a model which improves the charging efficiency of the solar system by considering all the limitations of the current charge controllers.

Keywords: Solar system, Charge Controller, Efficiency, PWM, Transistor, MPPT.

1. Introduction:

For every country electrical energy is one of the prime requirements. This energy is needed for all the domestic activities, industrial activities, entertainments, education, agriculture and many more. The energy sector of India is one of the major sectors for the economic growth. As on 30th June 2017 the installed capacity of electrical energy to the national grid is 329.23 GW. [1] The gross electrical energy generated in the year 201-17 by utilities and non utilities is found to be

1433.4 TW. [2] India is found to be the third largest producer of electrical energy and fourth largest consumer of the energy. [3]

In India the energy production and demand ratio is not 1:1. The demand is always more than the production. Moreover the electricity produced by companies and distributed by companies controlled by government are supplied to the urban areas and industrial areas than rural areas. The rural electrification has become very difficult for installation as well as maintenance. This is due to the factor that the houses in the rural area are not dense. One can see more of agricultural land than houses in rural area. The initial set up cost and maintenance cost is considerably high. This made the companies not to show interest in providing electricity to the rural areas. In India we are generating electricity using two major methods. They are

1. energy from non renewable energy resources
2. Energy from renewable energy resources.

1.1.1 Energy from non renewable energy resource

This is a traditional method of producing electricity using the following commercial methods

- Hydro electric Plants
- Thermal electric Plants
- Atomic electric Plants

In case of Hydro Electric plants the water flowing in a river is blocked by means of a dam and the water is canalised to rotate the huge turbines. These turbines generate electricity. This electrical energy thus generated will be sent to different distribution centres and then from the distribution centre it is distributed to individual houses or industries. Here the production centre is far away from the end users. Also the capacity of the electrical energy production depends on the amount of water stored in a dam which in turn depends on the seasonal rain fall. As on 30th of April 2017 our country is able to produce 44,594 MW of power from hydro electricity.[4] This makes India a 7th largest country producing hydro electricity. The capacity of the electrical energy produced from hydro electricity is 13.5% of total utility power supply. The electricity from hydro electric power station has certain drawbacks. The hydro electric plants depend upon the rain water storage which is highly uncertain. The distance between the production centre, distribution centre and end users is too much normally few hundreds of kilometres. This causes a major power loss in between in the form of heat. The supply of this energy is highly insecure as the open wires carry heavy current for a distance of several hundred kilometres. Due to natural storms or heavy wind blow or rain may cause damage to the wires which carry heavy current. In

such case the end users may not get the energy as well as the surrounding people where the wire carrying heavy current breaks down will be having the life threat.

The major source of production of electrical energy is from the thermal energy which makes use of steam to rotate the generators. The steam is generated from the coal. The thermal electric plants cause a lot of pollution to the environment.

A small portion of energy is generated from the atomic plants. The atomic plants depend upon the uranium which is dangerous to the environment.

1.1.2 Energy from renewable energy resources.

An alternative method of production of energy is from renewable energy sources. These are the energy sources which do not pollute the environment. These energy resources make use of the environmental energy and convert them to electrical energy like wind blow to electricity, sun light to electricity, under water current to electricity, waste product to electricity etc.[5] These energy resources are also called green energy resources. One among them is the solar energy where in the solar Photo Voltaic modules convert the sun light into electrical energy. This form of energy is becoming more and more popular now. This type of energy can be produced at a large scale if a large plane surface is available. This type of energy production can be done at a large scale or commercial scale.[6] Solar energy can also be generated for an individual house at a small scale.

Wind energy is also another form of energy wherein the large scale wind blades are connected to a wind turbine and then this device is installed at a height where there is a large amount of wind blow is there. This type of wind turbines are costly and are used only as an alternative additive energy source to a commercial energy. [7]

The under water current usually found inside the ocean are used to generate electricity. A large scale under water turbines are installed beneath the ocean . The current is generated from these turbines when the waves are moving towards the sea shore. [8]

1.2 Need of charge controllers:

The electrical energy generated from the solar PV (photo Voltaic) cells are used for running appliances. It is also necessary to store the energy when the energy is not used by the load. To store the solar energy in the day time necessary battery backup is required. The solar panels can not be directly connected to the battery backup because the energy varies with the sun light. To protect the battery backup it is very much necessary to use the charge controller which controls the flow of electrical energy flow towards the battery. A lot of research activities are done in

improving the performance of the solar charge controllers. Presently there are three different types of charge controllers observed for solar system namely Shunt transistor switch based charge controller, PWM solar charge controller and recent MPPT based charge controller.[9]

2. A review on solar charge controllers

Hogrefe, A., & Sullivan, R. (1973) [10] has mentioned in his paper that an automatic charge controller is required to charge the battery backup using the solar energy. In his paper he mentioned the usage of charge controller in the space craft system where in the controller measures the current in ampere, the charging and discharging rate of battery. The charge controller is maintaining the battery fully charged. In this paper he has mentioned the use of the circuit designed using the bipolar quantizer to monitor the charging and discharging of the battery in the space craft.

Whittaker, J. R. (1987). [11] has mentioned the need of a blocking diode which blocks the reverse supply from the battery to the panel during night. He also mentioned about the reference voltage which is temperature sensitive as an input to the voltage comparator. The other input being the variation in the voltage which is taken from the solar panel used to charge the battery under normal condition. The charge controller is using a pulse width modulated output for the charging. This PWM charge controller is controlled by the output of the comparator.

Schoeman, J. J., & Wyk, J. V. (1982, June). [12] has mentioned the V-I characteristics of the solar panel with ambient temperature, insulation from such a panel. He described the application of a darlington circuit to saturate the voltage by compensating voltage. He used the advanced switching technology to reduce the loss inured by the switching.

Kashima, Y., & Yoshida, M. (1980). [13] mentioned in the paper that the control system for the solar battery charger having the solar systems connected in series for charging the battery, the total system is used to drive a heavy load require a control system which prevents the battery backup from over charging. Since the solar panels are in series the amount of energy coming towards the battery backup will be heavy. So it is very much essential to design a controlling system to prevent the battery backup from overcharging.

Arai, S. (2002). [14] has mentioned that the charging system is a voltage converter which converts the original voltage generated from the solar panel into charging voltage to charge the backup to its required level. Here the voltage converter is operating depending on the driving clock whose duty cycle is varying based on the charged power stored in the battery backup.

Riawan, D. C., et.al (2007, December). [15] have designed a solar charge controller using a cuk converter. Here the power generated from the solar PV cells is transferred to the battery backup

using cuk dc/dc converter. This converter is working in a Parallel Power Transfer Mode. This mode achieves a higher efficiency. This technique adopts the PWM based MPPT algorithm to extract the maximum power from the solar PV cells.

Masoum, M. A., et.al (2004) [16] have mentioned in his paper that the battery's operating voltage is forced near the solar cell's maximum power point. This situation is maintained under all the conditions of the environment. The solar arrays perform their optimal operations using VMPPT-Voltage Optimum Power Point Tracking. He also mentioned that the advantage of such solar chargers is the charger require shorter time period for the charging and it is of low cost.

Chuang, Y. C., & Ke, Y. L. (2007). [17] has mentioned the advantage of the high frequency resonant converter in solar energy battery charger. He mentioned that the above type of converters offer a low switching loss and a high power density. The type of chargers have low EMI due to which the performance of the charger is improved.

Koutroulis, E., & Kalaitzakis, K. (2004). [18] have mentioned in the paper that the battery life time can be increased by using MPPT based solar charge controller because of the higher level of solar charging. The control process of charging does not depend upon the current measurements of the battery. The effect of the current sensor sensitivity on the battery will be reduced. Here the principle of battery charging is based on the battery current regulation, the large string batteries can use these principles.

Nguyen, T. T., et.al (2013). [19] have mentioned in the paper that a simplified MPPT solar charge controller can be used at the roof top of the vehicles which run using solar energy. The charge controller is simpler at its structure, shorter time for charging, uses a buck converter with the digital signal processing as a controller.

Yau, H. T., Lin, C. J., & Liang, Q. C. (2013). [20] have mentioned the use of PSO based PI controller design which uses DC to DC boost converter for the solar power generation using variable step size incremental conductance method (VSINC). This technique is used to enable the solar cell to track the maximum power at any time during the charging. This generated voltage is then converted to the required level using DC to DC buck converter. The charging system uses the constant voltage or constant current method to charge the battery.

Boico, F., Lehman, B., & Shujaee, K. (2007). [21] have written the drawbacks of the current charge controllers when they are connected to the solar arrays. The various parameters like position, temperature and other environmental conditions effect the performance of the charge controller when they are connected to the NiMH batteries. This article has given a new idea

about the temperature based charge controller technique. The article also highlights the need of MPPT technology embedded within a microcontroller.

Patil, A. R., Atar, et.al (2013) [22] have given an embedded fuzzy module for the charge control. This module reads the real time voltage and the current of the battery. The fuzzy module uses the PWM based charge controller technique. This system is embedded in the PIC Microcontroller. This technique helps in smooth charging of a battery during critical phase of the battery also. The PIC microcontroller unit is programmed using the fuzzy logic. This logic decides the duty cycle of the PWM charging.

Amin, N., et.al. (2009, June). [23] have presented the cost efficient solar charger controller with the disconnect and reconnect battery and load function during battery overcharging and under discharging. The model proposed is having an efficient disconnecting and reconnecting action and this is really helpful in protecting the battery and the load. The paper has mentioned the usage of PIC microcontroller which has the program written in C.

Pfeifer, J. E., et.al (2008). [24] have written that the charge controller contains an input interface which is used to convert the input dc into output dc signals. The meaning of a controller is operable coupled to the converter section, for operating the converter section at an estimated maximum power point of the input DC electrical signals. The estimated maximum power point is delivered by a control scheme which is used to quickly adopt to changing condition for getting the optimum energy harvest and improved energy conversion efficiency.

Ramaprabha, R., & Mathur, B. L. (2011). [25] have written that the charge controller is very much required solar PV system. They have also mentioned the use of buck-boost charge controller with MPPT technology. The voltage command is determined by both PV maximum power point tracking loop as well as the battery charging loop. The controller has a responsibility of balancing the power flow from the PV panel to the battery as well as to the load. The over all concept is to fully utilize the solar PV power.

Riawan, D. C., & Nayar, C. V. (2007, December). [26] have given an idea about the solar charger using cuk converter. This is a controller which makes use of DC/DC conversion technology. This converter is configured as a parallel power transfer mode (PPT). This mode gives a high efficiency. This controller uses a PWM method of solar charging.

Grzesiak, W. (2006, May). [27] have written a paper in which they have introduced the new charge controller for high voltage thin film PV modules. The PV modules use advanced CdTe technology. The output voltage of the PV panel is much higher than the traditional 12V/24V panels. This high DC PV panel's output voltage has to be transferred to the required lower value

by means of a DC/DC converter. The converter here used is a well known MPPT based converter to achieve a high efficiency in the performance.

Werulkar, A. S., & Kulkarni, P. S. (2012, December).[28] have described the design of microcontroller based soft switching buck converter. Here the converter design is done using zero current switching technique. The microcontroller is generating PWM switching signals for charging. The output voltage of the solar PV module is reduced to 15V and then applied to the charge controller circuit. This device has overcharge protection and undercharge alarm technique. The microcontroller which is used here is AVR controller.

Hiwale, S., Patil, M. V., & Vinchurkar, H. (2014). [29] have written a paper in which they have mentioned the Maximum Power Point Tracker (MPPT) technology for the solar PV charge controllers to charge the battery. The output power of the PV system continuously varies depending upon the irradiance and temperature of the PV panel. The main objective of the charge controller is to improve the efficiency of the charging system. The proposed system here is using Perturb & Observe (P&O) of the MPPT technique where when the irradiation and temperature are either constant or slowly varying then the P&O tracks the MPP steadily and calculates the operating point where the battery gets the maximum charge. This is achieved through the buck converter.

Halder, T. (2011, January). [30] has explained the solar charge controller which charges the battery using the solar energy generated from PV modules. This charge controller uses DC/DC converter system for charging. The charge controller is designed in such a way that it automatically disconnects the load when the power stored within the battery falls below a pre defined level. The load will be automatically reconnected when the battery power goes above the minimum level. These levels are pre programmed.

Singla, A., et.al (2014, December). [31] have designed a LVCMOS based charge sensor on FPGA. In the paper they stated that the life span of the battery in the solar energy system depends on how smoothly the charging and discharging of the same is done. The charge controller's responsibility is to smoothen the activity and to improve the efficiency of operation. The idea of LVCMOS technology is to reduce the power consumption of the charge controller. In the experimental setup variety of LVCMOS devices are used as input charge controllers and the performance efficiencies are noted down. The authors found around 60% reduction in the power consumption while using LCMOS15.

Khera, N., et.al (2015, December).[32] have designed a charge controller for solar PV systems with the feature of overcharge cut off, provision to block the reverse current flow at night. This

charge controller is helpful in maintaining the battery life for a long time period. The charge controller improves the power quality both at production as well as utilization.

Nema, P., Nema, R. K., & Rangnekar, S. (2009). [33] have mentioned the need of the hybrid charge controllers which combines the input energy from multiple renewable energy resources like solar, wind etc. This is to combine the energy from multiple sources. Multiple energy resources are the next generation idea as to get the maximum energy from the renewable resources. The paper gives importance to the hybrid energy system combining energy from multiple resources. The idea can be implemented using a proper charge controller which can combine the energy produced from multiple resources.

Sivagamasundari, et.al (2013). [34] have given importance to the MPPT based charge controllers which maximizes the power output of the solar PV cells. These charge controllers get maximum power from one or more solar panels. The Perturb and Observe method of the MPPT technology is the strategy that can be used to optimize the power output of an array. In this method the voltage of the controller is adjusted by a small amount if there is any increase in the input power. Further the same is seen if there is a further increase in the input power. This type of adjustment in the output voltage is called buck boost converter system. By varying the buck boost converter's duty cycle the source and load impedance will be matched and the efficiency of the system is improved.

Jing, H., & Jiancheng, Z. (2009). [35] have written in the paper about the new technique of MPPT charge control which is called Novel MPPT algorithm. This algorithm is based on the numerical method for Photo Voltaic system. This algorithm is able to perform the MPPT with one step quadratic interpolation. The constant voltage tracking system (CVT) is used in the MPPT method to ensure the enhancement in the speed.

Al-Mashhadany, Y. I., & Attia, H. A. (2014). [36] have introduced a small and portable charger for low power devices. This charger contains two inputs input AC and solar. This charger is used for 9V batteries. This charger has two speed charging. The charging current is limited to 100ma. This charger can charge two types of cellular batteries either 5.7V or 3.7V. The charging current is 10% of the battery current (1000mah).

Yang, L. I. U., et.al (2011). [37] have written a paper where in the charge controller is designed using LT3652 a monolithic battery charger which operates over 4.95V to 32V input voltage range. This IC has a constant voltage and current charge characteristics with 2A maximum current. This charger uses a 3.3V float voltage as a feedback voltage as a reference. This IC employs a voltage regulation loop for input. This reduces the charge current if the input voltage is below the programmed voltage.

Ingole, J. N., et.al (2012). [38] have mentioned about the PIC based solar charge controller for the battery. In this paper they have used PIC16F72 as a solar charge controller for controlling the battery overcharging as well as deep discharging below a certain limit. This device limits the variable input voltage to 12.8V. This voltage is the voltage of a fully charged solar battery. The cut off voltage of the battery is limited to 10.8V. This charge controller is used for small size solar system which can be used for domestic appliances.

Wagner, R., & Sauer, D. U. (2001). [39] have written a paper for the charging strategies for valve-regulated lead/acid batteries in solar power applications. These types of charge controllers are useful for gel and AGM batteries. The different types of charging techniques were tested at different places for two years with the same loading and same solar generators. It is observed that it is not possible to charge the batteries to the full extent. So it is very important to see to it that the battery charge controllers must be designed so as to improve the life of the batteries. The battery life depends upon the charging and discharging style which is controlled by the charge controllers.

Bhandari, B., et.al (2014).[40] have written in their paper about the off grid hybrid charge controller which could combine solar, wind and hydro electricity. The paper presents the study of availability of the wind speed, solar radiation and micro hydro flow in the high altitude of Nepal. Then the idea of getting the combined effect of the three energy resources together to facilitate the mini grid. The controller has a hybrid output by the combination of solar, wind and small hydro electric projects and the output is supplied to a small grid.

Wallies Thounaojam, V., & Balekundri, A. (2014). [41] have developed a microcontroller based solar charge controller which uses a microcontroller PIC16F876A for charging the battery backup. The PIC16F876A is a CMOS Flash based 8 bit micro controller. This controller has 256 bytes of memory in EEPROM. This EEPROM is used to store the program of the performance. This microcontroller controls the PWM duty cycle which controls the charging of the battery. This device can operate at the voltage range of 2V to 5.5V.

Raveendhra, D., et.al (2013, March). [42] have designed a FPGA based open circuit voltage MPPT charge controller for solar PV system. This charge controller uses the principle of MPPT technology where in all the time the maximum power from the solar PV system is extracted to store in the battery backup. This concept is applicable under all conditions. The charge controller uses mathematical modelling of DC-DC converter and small signal analysis.

Akkaya, R., & Kulaksiz, A. A. (2004). [43] have designed a microcontroller-based stand-alone photovoltaic power system for residential appliances. In their paper they mentioned about the sun tracker system where the panel is adjusted to perpendicular to the incoming of sun light. The

charge method is closed loop current control of buck-boost DC-DC converter. A PWM inverter is used to convert the DC voltage to AC for the load.

3. Conclusion:

The various authors have mentioned the importance of the solar charge controller. There are various charge controllers for the solar system ranging from the simple charge controller to the complicated charge controllers. The charge controller may be designed using a simple shunt transistor or a PWM charger. The most recent charging technique used is the MPPT charge controllers which make use of the solar energy stored or utilized to the maximum extent. There are different algorithms used in the MPPT technology. So there is a research activity required by using a new algorithm which makes use of MPPT technique as well as PWM technique to improve the charging efficiency as well as designing a hybrid charger in the coming days.

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